

The Impact of Cultural and Natural Heritage Conservation on Tourism Development in the Municipality of Banaue, IFUGAO

A Research Study

Presented to the
Faculty of the College of Arts and Sciences
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management

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DEDICATION

This study is wholeheartedly dedicated to our beloved parents and family, who have been our source of inspiration and gave strength when we thought of giving up, and who continually provide financially, spiritually, emotionally, and always giving an advice.

To our adviser, friends, and classmates who shared their words of advice and encouragement to finish this research.

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ABSTRACT

Batad and Bangaan Ifugao inscribed as a World Heritage Site by the UNESCO the Ifugao rice terraces. However, in spite of the fact that it is considered a living sustainable heritage but some of the cultural and natural resources are not yet maintain, it is hypothesized that the conservation are not immune to the impacts brought about by social , cultural and economic. This study aimed to determine the estimated level answered by the respondents. To do this, efforts and strategies implemented with a 100% total, profile of the respondents with a 3.5 overall mean, economy impact with a total of 100%, social impact with a total of 100% and cultural with a 7.44 %total of responses. This indicates that the IMPACT OF CULTURAL AND NATURAL HERITAGE CONSERVATION ON TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF BANAUE, IFUGAO wasn't maintained.

Keywords:- Ifugao Rice Terraces, Conservation, Sustainable Development, Cultural And Natural Resources.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

One of the most important ways tourism can protect cultural and natural heritage is through community empowerment (Solimar International Tourism

Consultants, 2021). The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) states that the best way to secure a single heritage is through collective responsibility and a powerful side to monitor peace. By providing an integrated set of conventions on the protection of heritage, UNESCO creates a unique platform for international cooperation and dialogue, promotes natural respect, understanding, and development of appreciation. However, UNESCO (2020) is highlighting the importance of the biodiversity of tangible and intangible heritage, which should be celebrated on every 18th of April yearly. Heritage is celebrated because it comes from a birth or belongs to a heritage, the customs and practices passed down through the years, and the world heritage site consists of cultural or natural sites that have been recognized as worthy of preservation and conservation.

The best way to secure one heritage according to UNESCO is a collective responsibility, as well as a powerful rear of monitoring peace, while Community empowerment is one of the most effective ways that tourism can protect cultural and natural heritage (Solimar International Tourism Consultants, 2021). UNESCO is known as the "intellectual" agency of the United Nations. People must rely on the power of intelligence that could sustain the hope of humanism to build peace and progress, so sustainable development must be elected. Additionally, through a comprehensive set of conventions concerning heritage, UNESCO offers a unique platform for international cooperation and dialogue, promoting natural respect and understanding as well as the appreciation that evolved.

UNESCO (2020), on the other hand, emphasizes the value of celebrating the variety of tangible and intangible heritage on April 18 every year. A person's heritage is something they celebrate because of their birth and the customs that have been passed down through the years, whereas a global heritage site is made up of natural or cultural landmarks that have been deemed important enough to be conserved. The researchers' information focused on the impact of cultural and natural heritage conservation on tourism development in the municipality of Banaue, Ifugao. Researchers also discuss various factors, why it is necessary to conserve Banaue's heritage sites. Some of the effects of abandoned historic sites or objectives are also mentioned to better understand why researchers chose the study and suggested solutions to the study gap. According to Historic Environment Scotland (2022), World Heritage Sites are "universal cultural and natural sites of outstanding value" with significant value for all generations of the world, and in order to preserve such sites, UNESCO seeks to protect and preserve these sites through the World Cultural and Natural Heritage Protection Convention. This era was defined in 1971 as an international treaty, requiring governments of countries that had signed the declaration of the treaty to identify and designate appropriate places to be listed on the UNESCO-protected and maintained list. Problems such as the abandonment of heritage and object sites have been observed in several countries where there is a lack of knowledge and information on how enormous heritage contributes to the country's revenue. It attracts people who are interested in discovering and knowing the existence of other cultures and practices. Tourism is a way to attract all foreigners to visit heritage sites. However, there are several reasons people abandon a place or object, and the UNESCO World Heritage Convention has shared several reasons: armed conflict and war, earthquakes, natural disasters, pollution, poaching, uncontrolled urbanization and unmonitored tourism development. According to Harper (2020), a nation's strength is largely built on connections with the past. The past is evident in the buildings built by our ancestors, and no one can deny that it enriches our lives and raises awareness to understand more culture. Heritage is the collection of living images of ancient images that men cherish and value because of the memories they create. To address research gaps, researchers applied quantitative approaches because they were the methods of research necessary for the growth of any organization. It requires a large number of people, because their search unit is to work with the local government unit, tourism stakeholders and the community to fill the gap. Granicus (2023) explains that the importance of community involvement has become a center of functioning democracy. Building a constructive relationship between the communities and the government's necessary institutions to ensure equitable and sustainable public decisions and improve the lives of residents is necessary. Researchers believe that ineffective community relationships lead to frustration and disintegration between public organizations and local governments, so the establishment and maintenance.

The World Heritage Day was founded in 1982, and the International Conference on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) named 18 April the World Heritage Day, which was approved by the UNESCO General Assembly in 1983. This day aims to raise awareness around the world about the importance of cultural heritage, monuments and the need for their protection and preservation. UNESCO gradually defines two types of world heritage sites (WHS), including historic buildings and monuments, cultural sites. Natural heritage is the river, the mountains and other landscapes. In addition, UNESCO also introduced the three types of heritage, namely cultural property, intangible cultural heritage and natural heritage. In cultural property or material culture, tangible property includes buildings, monuments, historical sites and artifacts. These valuable objects provide important discoveries for scientific experiments, archaeological and architectural research. These mobile objects include books, documents, artworks, machines and clothing; these mobile objects include monuments, buildings and frescoes. All of this is important for mankind because it provides physical evidence of past ideas, and all of these objects and historical sites are a source of endless history. For intangible culture, these are non-physical heritage. This tradition may originate from the ancestors and pass through their descendants or social customs. Oral traditions and performance arts social practices are related to natural, atomic or traditional

craftsman knowledge and skills. Food and medicine are also one of the most important examples of heritage. Intangible heritage includes language, traditional dance and ceremonial dance.

Naturally, intangible cultural heritage is more difficult to preserve than tangible heritage and is heavily dependent on stories and folklore. The third type of heritage is natural heritage consisting of the whole natural environment, biodiversity (flora and fauna), and geological elements. In 1972, a dialogue on the preservation of world cultural and natural heritage set out the requirements for the "unprecedented universal value" that a place must have. In 2020, 1,121 World Heritage Sites (869 cultural, 213 natural and 39 mixed) will be selected in 167 countries. Unique landmarks, geographically and historically recognizable, with unique cultural and physical characteristics. The Convention requires at least one of the ten cultural and natural criteria to be included in the world heritage: first, diversity of human values, second, development of forms of urban or settled settlements, third, references to history and living traditions, fourth, superlative natural phenomena, fifth, evidence of geological, biological and ecological processes and finally, the conservation of biodiversity on the ground. The Convention was organized to protect humanity's common cultural and natural heritage. Consequently, all UNESCO World Heritage Sites are monitored by international treaties. All this heritage belongs to people all over the world, regardless of the territory they are located in.

One Green Planet (2020) proposed five (5) things people should do to preserve a heritage and was supported by Potter (2022) by sharing other tips for the preservation and conservation of important sites. According to the special events of these two conservationists, such as workshops and lectures, the following are needed on this issue: First, create a volunteer group to work with interested residents, who love to preserve the recent memory of this community's advocate by creating a website and maintaining a discussion of the Board. It is also advantageous to open up the community for tours and other special events. Secondly, provide tours- organize and create self-guided driving tours accompanied by brochures for visitors on historical sites. Third, organize special events – encourage people interested in mid-century architecture to engage with other people who are interested in recognizing the organization and raise funds through a special exhibition with right parties focused on architecture, modern heritage, and a series of lectures by local historians. Fourthly, a list of threats to a protected place a list of problems to the local authority regarding neglect, destruction and change to raise awareness and enlarge public knowledge of its preservation. Fifth, conduct community workshops-begin to teach the basic parts are to preserve heritage sites. Workshops and seminars area means of educating specific audiences about the recent past and teaching those interested in building proper architecture techniques to repair or replace their original appearance. Sixth, to educate those involved in the decision-making process - the aim of adequate education on these mid-century resources is to build trust and in-depth knowledge of the historic sites that could be a source of potential post-war market and successfully promote them to tourism Seventh, to study the resources from the recent past that focus on preserving and protecting and always to educate the community in order to create and establish a historical context for future research and visits. Eighth, evaluate property and determine whether it meets the criteria of the national registry, and finally, make the case for the significance of the site. Employ it clearly, because it is a way of understanding cultural heritage of different communities, and also a bridge to intercultural dialogue, to promote the natural respect of other ways of life.

Tourism is often seen to the conservation of world heritage. Our World Heritage (2021) stated that, in presenting heritage to the public, tourism as inappropriate platform to strengthen historic heritage, guaranteeing its economic and social viability. In this study, the main aim is to create a theme of heritage tourism with an imperative reciprocal relationship in which both can be exposed to critical changes, but the good to review the interrelationship is crucial. Deconstruction of old concepts and reconstruction of new ones that is collaborative to the current challenges. Synergies must be rebuilt and strengthened as a guarantee of continuity and resilience, and the sustainability of heritage and tourism at the same time. In Amen's study (2021), this may seem absurd, but tourism play sa dominant role in the conservation of cultural and natural heritage, because both heritage and tourism are linked to the promotion of tourism, which increases the accumulation of financial resources for the preservation and conservation of heritage sites. In tourism, people need to be immersed through normal borders and part of the physical and cultural differences in order to fully appreciate the beauty of a heritage site. To be visible in tourism, no one will ever appreciate the intimate beauty of a heritage from a distance. Anyone can put profit first, but the guarantee of preserving heritage must be given priority. Tourism helps communities financially, but communities must always be aware of the balance of culture and heritage in order not to compromise the two variables.

National and Cultural Heritage Philippines on March 25, 2009. The National Cultural Heritage Act, officially designated as Republic Act No. 10066, is a Philippines law that created the Philippines Registry of cultural. Moreover, to pressure Filipino's heraldry works. The National Historical Commission of the Philippines (NHCP) or in Filipino language coined as: Pambansang Komisyon ng Pangkasaysayan ng Pilipinas. This is a government agency of the Philippines, and its mission is to promote Philippine's history and cultural heritage through research, dissemination, conservation sites management and heraldry works. Its goal is to inculcate appreciation, pride, and awareness to Filipino spirits that the Philippines has a very illustrious heroes creating noble deeds that enriches Philippine's history. However, the NHCP was formed in 1933 and was established only in 1972 as a part of President Ferdinand Marcos declaration of

Martial Law. The original source of NHCP is dated back in 1933 when the American Colonial insular Government first established the Philippines Historical Research and Markers Committee (PHKMC) but it was replaced by Philippines Historical Committee to n 1935 order the Philippine commonwealth. After the World War II, the reconstruction of PHC lightened, marketing 400 historical sites and objects that led to the merging of all historical commission into National Heroes Commission in 1963.

In July 1965, Republic Act No. 4368 otherwise known as the National Historical Commission (NHC). This act abolishes PHC and the National Heroes Commission. The functions of NHC are to publish, preserve, research, compile and mark historical events, sites, published works related to Philippine history. And in 1972, NHC was renamed into National Historical Institute (NHI) under the recognition of Martial Law. But 38 years later, President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo signal Republic Act No. 10086 law reverting NHI into its original form known as: National Historical Commission of the Philippines.

The National Historical Commission of the Philippines (NHCP) requires the following to quality an extant of heritage value. a.) For immovable Cultural Property, it showed he notified to the Registry of Deeds for annotation on the land titles. b.) For the local Government units, though the cultural officers maintain inventory of cultural property and shall finished the Commission a copy. c.) All government agencies and instrumentalities [government owned and controlled corporations] must report ownership or possession to qualified cultural offices or agencies of such object and must be immediately register to the Commission, and Private Collections and owners of cultural property will always own the extant even after registration and could remain confidential/prior consent of the owner.

The University of Santo Tomas under the leadership of Zerrudu (2020) delivered a webinar lecture in the Department of Tourism's (DOT) online learning Series. The theme for the 2020 National Heritage Month is "Mga kwentong Pamana"(Stories of Heritage). The purpose is to highlight the social and cultural impact of Filipino heritage in the preservation of the country's legacies that is extreme with tourism. The speaker also said make our heritage meaningful, the community should also equate themselves in making time meaningful. Humans have to functional and useful in keeping tradition and stories alive because it is showed people survive.

According to Del Rosario (2020) heritage is shared by the whole community that is why it should be taken care of and promote this ruins or site attract more people to visit and learn from the historic extant. The following are the reasons why preservation of heritage is a tool to foster tourism: a.) It entices more tourists to come to the Philippines b.) Heritage site is source of identity that can be laid out programs and projects that provides more financial resources c.) It is a pride of every country d.) It could be a platform of every political recognition, a medium for intercultural dialogue, means for ethical reflection, and the potential basis for local economic development and e.) It impresses more tourists to stay longer and spend more money.

Nowadays tourism is highly competitive communities with heritage assets should establish heritage structure and landscape as economic assets. Focus on the qualities that will make your community stand out from the rest of the world; address these visitors with utmost respect because experience is the best feature to differentiate the place from anywhere else. Try to elicit an emotional relationship amongst the visitors in promoting tourism development.

COVID – 19 has had a major impact on tourism and takes time to restore the industry due to changes in tourism behaviour caused by the virus. The study helps readers explore the impact of the conservation of the cultural and natural heritage of Banaue and its impact on tourism development. The relationship between the two variables depends on how the study population reacts to self-constructing questionnaires. Sing'ansbi and Lwoga (2018) confirmed that when preserving heritage, the host community does not simply rely on the heritage or the theme to attract visitors, but that what is most needed to promote tourism is the affective dimension of motivations that create a sense of cultural attachment. The Philippine Development Plan (PDP, 2022) reiterates that the Philippines is a diverse cultured nation, but the government is trying to build a database in which cultural experts can gather the collected data due to the lack of financial resources and limited knowledge of the preservation of social science. In addition, the PDP prioritizes:

a) the preservation and security of Filipino cultural heritage) the promotion of equitable and inclusive access to cultural resources and services' and: c) the preservation and enhancement of cultural assets that promote creativity and innovation for social and economic growth. Mondoneda (2021) said that the Ifugao's continued to flourish and were sufficiently themselves. Despite globalization, many traditions are under pressure. Ifugaos music, dance, rituals, folklore, wood carving, agricultural and forestry practices still exist and are still practiced. For centuries, the Ifugaos lived creativity; armed with wit and engineering know-how, the Ifugao ancestors were able to cultivate unforgiving mountainous areas centuries ago of a united community is a tool for poverty-free living.

In May 2018, Mayor Jerry U. Dalipog carried out a program to help the heritage site, such as the obstructive sewage tanks to prevent the drainage of waste water into rivers, the parking structure for 114 vehicles to keep tourists cars, the parking garage for vehicles to avoid traffic jams, the repair and rehabilitation of damaged terraces, including hiking trails, currently there are 1607 damaged terraces, which are restored with the help of the Department of Public Works and Highways (DENR) and the Tourism

Infrastructure and Ifugao always and continues to practice the ancient tradition of maintaining the "muyong or forest areas on the terrace - usually at the top of the mountain. UNESCO has also introduced property correction measures (2010), such as:

a)the establishment of functional management at the provincial level; b)land-zoning and land-use plans; c)the implementation of regulations for tourism and infrastructure development's; d) a five-year plan for local government to maintain rice terraces and irrigation systems; e)the determination of the critical areas for the environmental impact assessment (EAT) of proposed development; and f)strengthening the reforestation program including species to protect the water. Finally, the researcher focuses on cultural and natural conservation of heritage sites and its effects on tourism development through the participation of communities and local governments.

A. Theoretical Framework

The decline of the Bangaan and Batad Rice Terraces, two of the birthplaces of the eighth wonder of the world, are creating issues for the community and the local government of Banaue, Ifugao since these historical monuments represent a significant source of income for the locals. Consequently, plans, initiatives, and funds have already been decided upon and secured in order to conserve this historical heritage in partnership with the local community. This encouraged more visitors in Banaue to stay longer. In this study, Cesare Brondi defined restoration theory (1963) as any intervention that allowed the product of human activity to be recognized its physical being and historical nature, in view of its transmission to the future. This theory is proof that 60 years ago someone inspired thereto value human works, because today it is the heritage main attraction of the tourist influx.

B. Research Paradigm

The research paradigm shows the variables that are needed in this study. This study utilized the Input-Process-Output Method (IPO). These variables were the key points to produce the outcomes.

Fig 1: Research Paradigm of the study

C. Statement of the Problem➤ *This Study Sought to Answer the Following Questions;*

- what are the current conservation efforts and strategies implemented to protect the cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue?
- what is the level of tourism development and visitor satisfaction in Banaue, considering its cultural and natural heritage sites:
 - ✓ profile of Local Communities;
 - ✓ profile of Tourism Officer and Local Government Units; and
 - ✓ profile of Tourist?
- what are the impacts of tourism development resulting from the conservation of cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue in terms of:
 - ✓ Economic Impact;
 - ✓ Social Impact; and
 - ✓ Cultural Impact?

D. Objective of the Study

These research objectives guide the study about the impact of cultural and natural heritage conservation on tourism development in the municipality of Banaue, Ifugao. By addressing these objectives, the research can contribute to a better understanding of how heritage conservation efforts can impact the tourism industry and provide valuable insights for sustainable tourism development in the region.

- To determine the current conservation efforts and strategies implemented to protect the cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue.
- To describe the level of tourism development and visitor satisfaction in Banaue considering its cultural and natural heritage sites.
- To determine the impacts of tourism development resulting from the conservation of cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue.

E. Significance of the Study

The study was conducted to know if conserving cultural and natural heritage affects tourism development. It aimed to provide credible information regarding the chosen topic from the respondents. The results of the research will be of great benefits to the following:

- **STUDENTS.** The result provided the student with some knowledge on heritage conservation and its effects to tourism development. It will give the student the realization that a heritage site is a major attraction of tourism and thus, being the source of income to the community. At the end of the study, the student would have finally known there should be a reciprocal relation between heritage and tourism.
- **INSTRUCTORS.** The compiled data guided the instructors to know more about the relation of heritage and tourism, that must be valued by everyone and help conserve heritage site or the environment.
- **COMMUNITY.** Not all residents of the community are aware of the positive effects of heritage and tourism development. This research would inspire all residents to be responsible and they give support to all the programs of the LGU towards fostering livelihood through tourism.
- **CONSERVATORS.** This study would aid them to their discussion and programs related to the study and significantly the indispensable to the conservation of the heritage.
- **LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNITS.** It helped local administrators know concerning issues related to the study. This enlightened them to be accurate and precise in formulating laws, programs, or ordinances in relation to the research.
- **TOURIST (International and Domestic).** Provided opportunities for cultural exchange and understanding, as their visits led to sharing of diverse perspective and traditions. This created more enriched experience for both the visitors and local community, fostering a deeper appreciation for the destination.
- **DEPARTMENT OF TOURISM.** The result of the study provided complete and balanced data that enabled them to develop future action plans for the full recovery of the heritage sites involving tourism development.

F. Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was conducted purposely to find out the heritage conservation and its effects to the development of tourism. The researchers used latest studies and citations within five years of time frame to present. These references was used in discovering conservation of heritage effects on tourism development. This study did not extend to other form of historic heritage and other factors affecting tourism in Batad and Banaan.

CHAPTER TWO METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents and discusses the research design, population and local, locale of the study, respondents of the study, data gathering procedure, research instrument, and statistical treatment of data. The research was conducted in order to determine the impact of cultural and natural heritage site in Bangaan and Batad. In order to answer this research study, the researcher opted to obtain the view of local communities, LGUs/ tourism officers and some tourists in line with the topic. The participants answered a survey questionnaire structured in a check list and Likert scale format. Data gathered from this research instrument were computed for interpretation.

A. Research Design

The study used the quantitative method of research. According to International Research (2018) quantitative research is a structured way of collecting and analyzing data obtained from different sources. It also involves the application of computation and statistical tools to extract results. It is known that quantitative research tries to quantify the problem and understand results from large population. However, the survey questionnaire employs basic approach of using questionnaire.

B. Population and Local

The sample size was determined through probability sampling. Since probability approach deals with large population, the researchers chose the locals, local government unit (LGU), tourism officers and tourist (foreigners).

The target population of this research consists of 55 people, from the LGUs and tourism officers of Banaue, Batad, Bangaan and the tourists. From the overall combined population of LGUs and tourism officers of Banaue, a sample size of 15 people were chosen to represent the population. From a population size of 899 a sample size of 15 people from Batad were chosen to represent the population and from a population size of 773 a sample size of 15 people from Bangaan were chosen to represent the population.

C. Locale of the Study

The research study was conducted in the municipality of Banaue, Ifugao, specifically in the heritage sites of Bangaan and Batad focusing on the conservation and its effect to the tourism industry. The municipality of Banaue was chosen for the study since it is the number one heritage tourism destination in the province of Ifugao.

Fig 2: Map of the Municipality of Banaue Ifugao
Source: Ifugao.gov.ph

D. Data Gathering Tools

The gathered data was tallied and summarized by the researchers. The data were subjected to statistical treatment. Before the researchers gathered the data, the questionnaire was reviewed and validated by the panel of experts in this field.

E. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are the tourism officers, tourist, and the local communities in the barangay of Batad and Bangaan, Banaue, Ifugao.

F. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers submitted a letter for the approval of the conduct of the study at the office of the municipal mayor together with the barangay captains of Batad and Bangaan. The researchers administered the questionnaires (checklist) to the qualified respondents. The researchers explained the questions and concerns related to the questionnaires. The respondents answered the questionnaires and the researchers collected the data after all the respondents responded were done answering. The collected and gathered data were tallied and interpreted.

G. Research Instruments

The survey questionnaire (check list) was modified based on the research topic was developed by the researchers. It is composed of three (3) parts. The first part of the questionnaire is the profile of the respondents, second part is to determine the conservation efforts and strategies heritage implemented to protect the cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue, Ifugao. Lastly, to describe the level of tourism development and to determine the tourism development resulting from the preservation of cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue Ifugao.

H. Data Gathering Analysis

The study used the Likert Scale (1932) to calculate the total number of responses for each estimate level (Very satisfied, satisfied, neutral, and dissatisfied), Percentage, and mean.

Table 1: Likert Scale of Satisfaction

Scale	Description	Interpretation
4. 3.81-5.00	Very satisfied	Moderately Acceptable
3. 2.81-3.80	Satisfied	Acceptable
2. 1.81-2.80	Neutral	Fairly Acceptable
1. 0.99-1.80	Dissatisfied	Poorly Acceptable

Percentage (%)

Formula: $\% = f/N \times 100$

% = percentage

F = frequency

N = Total number of responses

Weighted mean:

Formula: $WX = wx/w$

CHAPTER THREE RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the collected quantitative data, this chapter summarizes the findings. The findings are arranged in tables and analyzed with qualitative interpretations to highlight the research’s goals and the questions it aims to address.

Table 2: Effort and Strategies Implemented

Efforts and Strategies Implemented	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Landscaping of paddies or the rice fields.	6	8.00	4
Registration to the National Commission on Cultures and Arts (NCCA)	5	6.67	5
Collaboration of stakeholders in giving and lending funds.	6	8.00	4
Cooperation of LGU and PLGU in monitoring the tourist attractions.	10	13.33	2
Racing seminars and workshops activities.	12	16.00	1
Implementing rules and regulations.	7	9.33	3
Zoning and land use plans.	4	5.33	6
Regulation over tourism and infrastructure development.	10	13.33	2
Regular maintenance and stabilization of the rice terraces and lifeline irrigation system.	10	13.33	2
Development control procedures.	5	6.67	5
Total	75	100	

Current Conservation Efforts and Strategies Implemented to Protect the Cultural and Natural Heritage Sites in Banaue

Table 2 shows the current conservation efforts and strategies implemented to protect the cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue. It can be gleaned that the most implemented effort and strategy is racing seminars and workshops activities with 12 (16%) responses. In addition, there are three (3) second most implemented effort and strategies namely cooperation of LGU and PLGU in monitoring the tourist attractions; regulation over tourism and infrastructure development; and regular maintenance and stabilization of the rice terraces and lifeline irrigation system with 10 (13.33%) responses respectively. Furthermore, implementing rules and regulations ranked as the third most implemented efforts and strategies having 7 (9.33%) responses. On the other hand, zoning and land use plants is the least implemented efforts and strategies with only 4 (5.33%) responses. Also, two efforts and strategies namely registration to the National Commission on Cultures and Arts (NCCA) and development control procedures ranked as the second least implemented having 5 (6.67%) responses. In addition, collaboration of stakeholders in giving and lending funds and landscaping of paddies or the rice fields ranked as the third least implemented efforts and strategies.

The result implies that raising seminars and workshops activities has the highest frequency (12) and zoning and land use plans has the least frequency (4) based on the result answered by the respondents.

Table 3: Profile of the Respondents

	Mean	Interpretation	Overall Mean	Overall Interpretation
Profile of Local Communities				
Bangaan	3	Satisfied	3.1	Satisfied
Batad	3.2	Satisfied		
Profile of LGU's and Tourism Officer				
Bangaan	2.93	Satisfied	3.03	Satisfied
Batad	3.13	Satisfied		
Profile of Tourists				
Bangaan	3.25	Satisfied	3.63	Very Satisfied
Batad	4	Very Satisfied		
Overall Mean			3.25	

A. Level of Tourism Development and Visitor Satisfaction in Banaue, Considering its Cultural and Natural Heritage Sites

Table 3 shows the level of tourism development and visitor satisfaction in Banaue, considering its cultural and natural heritage sites. It can be gleaned that the overall mean is 3.25 with a descriptive interpretation of satisfied. The result implies that the local community is satisfied with the natural and cultural heritage site.

Specifically, the local communities of Bangaan and Batad together with the LGU’s and Tourism Officers were satisfied with the tourism development as reflected by its overall mean of 3.1 and 3.03, respectively. This implies that barangay Bangaan and Batad together with the LGUs and officers are satisfied with the heritage site.

In addition, from the perspective of the tourists, the results from the two specified places, Banaue. Bangaan with a mean of 3.25, shows that the tourists are satisfied while Batad has a mean of 4 reflecting that tourist were very satisfied. This profile of tourists shows that Batad Rice terraces offers a more satisfactory travel experience compared to Bangaan as justified by the computed data.

Table 4: Economic Impacts

Economic Impacts	F	%	Rank
Increase livelihood	20	10.53	2
Improved infrastructure, irrigation	18	9.474	3
Promote economic proficiency	20	10.53	2
Increase in employment opportunities for locals, reducing unemployment rates.	22	11.58	1
Growth of the local economy through revenue generated from tourism-related businesses.	22	11.58	1
Generation of income through entrance fees, accommodation, and food expenses by tourists.	20	10.53	2
Enhanced investment in the tourism sector, leading to economic diversification.	14	7.368	5
Creation of entrepreneurial opportunities for locals.	16	8.421	4
Strengthening of the agricultural sector as tourism creates a demand for local produce.	20	10.53	2
Boost in government revenue through taxation and fees related to tourism activities.	18	9.474	3
Total	190	100	

B. Impacts of Tourism Development Resulting from the Conservation of Cultural and Natural Heritage Sites in Banaue

Table 4 shows the economic impacts of tourism development resulting from the preservation of cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue. It can be seen that there are two economic impacts that ranked first. These are increase in employment opportunities for locals, reducing unemployment rates and growth of the local economy through revenue generated from tourism-related businesses which has 22 (11.58) responses respectively. This suggest that the preservation of cultural and natural heritages hugely benefits the economy of the local community which serves as their primary source of living. These are followed by four second highest namely, increase livelihood, promote economic proficiency, generation of income through entrance fees, accommodation, and food expenses by tourists, and strengthening of the agricultural sector as tourism creates a demand for local produce having 20 (10.53%) responses. Next are improved infrastructure, irrigation and boost in government revenue through taxation and fees related to tourism activities having 18 (9.474%) responses.

It can also be seen that the enhanced investment in the tourism sector, leading to economic diversification has the least economic impact having 14 (7.368%) responses. The second least economic impact is the creation of entrepreneurial opportunities for locals with 16 (8.421%) responses, that suggests creating business to help locals from another sector.

Table 5: Social Impact

Social Impacts	F	%	Rank
Overcrowding	9	3.529	6
Review and improve regulations	18	7.059	5
Community union	18	7.059	5
Improvement of infrastructure and public services benefiting both tourists and residents.	26	10.2	1
Preservation of cultural heritage and traditions, fostering community pride and identity.	24	9.412	2
Creation of opportunities for cultural exchange between tourists and local communities.	20	7.843	4
Enhanced social integration and understanding between different cultures.	24	9.412	2
Empowerment of local communities through active participation in tourism development.	26	10.2	1
Preservation of traditional arts, crafts, and skills, ensuring their continuity.	24	9.412	2
Promotion of cultural education and awareness among locals and tourists.	24	9.412	2
Strengthening of community organizations and collaborations to protect local interests.	20	7.843	4
Improvement in the overall quality of life due to increased economic opportunities and access to services.	22	8.627	3
Total	255	100	

Table 5 shows the social impacts of tourism development resulting from the preservation of cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue.

There are 2 social impacts that ranked first. These are improvement of infrastructure and public services benefiting both tourists and local residents and empowerment of local communities through active participation in tourism development which has 26 (10.2%) responses. These are followed by four second highest namely: preservation of cultural heritage and traditions, fostering community pride and identity, enhanced social integration and understanding between different cultures, preservation of traditional arts, crafts, and skills, ensuring their continuity and promotion of cultural education and awareness among locals and tourists 24 (9.412%) . Next is improvement in the overall quality of life due to increased economic opportunities and access to services having 22 (8.627%) responses. It can be seen the creation of opportunities for cultural exchange between tourists and local communities and strengthening of community organizations and collaborations to protect local interests having 20 (7.43%) responses. The second least social impact having 18(7.059%) about the review and improve regulation and community union. The third least is the overcrowding which 9 (3.529%) responses.

The implication to this has the highest frequency 26 (10.2%) improvement of infrastructure and active participation that benefits local’s and officers and the least frequency 9 (3.529%) that overcrowding isn’t a problem to the site base on the question answered by the respondents.

Table 6: Cultural Impacts

Cultural Impacts	F	%	Rank
Intermarriages	15	6.20	5
Loss of native cultures	12	4.96	7
Multilingual education	15	6.20	5
Increasing cross cultural interaction	14	5.79	6
Preservation of traditional knowledge, customs, and practices, ensuring their continuity.	20	8.26	3
Increased appreciation and recognition of the local cultural heritage by tourists.	14	5.79	6
Revitalization of traditional arts, crafts, and music as they gain economic significance.	10	4.13	8
Protection of historical sites and ancient monuments, conserving the local history.	22	9.09	2
Promotion of cultural education, creating awareness and understanding among tourists.	24	9.92	1
Preservation and promotion of indigenous languages, helping to maintain linguistic diversity.	18	7.44	4
Safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage such as storytelling, rituals, and traditional practices.	20	8.26	3
Empowerment of local communities to actively participate in cultural preservation efforts.	18	7.44	4
Enhancement of cultural pride and identity among the local population.	22	9.09	2
Fostering intergenerational exchange, as younger generations learn from their elders and continue cultural traditions.	18	7.44	4
Total	242	100	

Table 6 shows the cultural impacts of tourism development resulting from the preservation of cultural and natural heritage sites in Banaue.

Based on the table, promotion of cultural education, creating awareness and understanding among tourists has a highest rank having 24 (9.92%) responses. These are followed by the two highest protections of historical sites and ancient monuments, conserving the local history and enhancement of cultural pride and identity among the local population having 22 (9.09%) responses. Preservation of traditional knowledge, customs, and practices, ensuring their continuity and safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage such as storytelling, rituals, and traditional practices which has 20 (8.26%) responses. Next are the 3 fourth ranked in cultural impacts namely preservation and promotion of indigenous languages, helping to maintain linguistic diversity, empowerment of local communities to actively participate in cultural preservation efforts and fostering intergenerational exchange, as younger generations learn from their elders and continue cultural traditions which has 18 (7.44%) responses.

The leading cultural impacts has the least which has a 15 (6.20%) namely intermarriages and multilingual education. Increasing cross cultural interaction and increased appreciation and recognition of the local cultural heritage by tourists which has 14 (5.79%) responses. Next is the loss of native cultures which has 12 (4.96%) responses and the fourth least in the cultural impact revitalization of traditional arts, crafts, and music as they gain economic significance which has 10 (4.13%) responses.

The implication to this part is that researchers know the result of the cultural impact has the highest about promoting our cultural education and raising awareness among tourists and least frequency result restore the traditional activities answered by the respondents.

According to Samovar, et al., (2010) distributed the cultural method into five elements of culture. The five elements of culture are language, value, history, social organization, religion. States about history is an outline which presents the way about how to people living in now and social life. Consequently, history conveys the culture from generation to generation.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

In conclusion, the study found out that;

The conservation efforts and strategies in the barangay of Batad and Bangaan, Banaue, Ifugao focus on raising seminars and workshops, cooperation between LGU's and PLGU's, and regulation over tourism. Most respondents in Bangaan and Batad are satisfied with the cultural and natural heritage site, with the highest satisfaction among those aged 31-60. The economic impacts of tourism development include increased employment opportunities and growth of the local economy, while the social impacts include improved infrastructure and conservation of cultural heritage. The cultural impacts focus on promoting cultural education and preserving historical sites.

B. Recommendations

Based on the research finding and analysis of the impact of cultural and natural heritage conservation in barangay Batad and Bangaan, Banaue, Ifugao and here are the recommendations:

- Development control procedures when it comes to infrastructure and the zoning land use plans for a better improvement of the heritage site (irrigation) and maintaining the use of tupeng.
- The communities should not continue building inns/houses in the paddies in able not to destroy the beauty of the rice terraces.
- Enhance investment for tourism sector that benefits to local communities and the tourism officer like environmental fees and budget to livelihood. The rules and regulations should be implementing, and homestay should be turnover to the barangay offices to have income.
- The LGU or PLGU should a lot of funds for conservation of the heritage sites.

